

CODEN [USA]: IAJPB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**A REVIEW ON EFFICACY AND SAFETY OF
HYDROXYCHLOROQUINE AGAINST VIRAL****Dr. Anique Ajmal¹, Dr. Jahanzeb Javed², Dr. Afshan Kiran³**¹ THQ Hospital, Sadiqabad, Rahim Yar Khan, ² Medical Officer at AJK Health Department, ³ WMO, THQ Hospital Sillanwali, Sargodha.**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Hydroxychloroquine [HCQ] belongs to the group of antimalarial agents with immunosuppressive, anti-autophagy, anti-inflammatory and anti-rheumatologic activities. In addition to reducing the manifestations of inflammatory disorders, Hydroxychloroquine is especially also associated with the prevention of disease and prevention of treatment-induced complications that include hyperlipidemia, diabetes mellitus, liver function test elevation and thrombosis. Hydroxychloroquine has shown promising results In-Vitro against SARS-CoV-1 [SARS- related Corona Virus strain 1], that caused the 2002-2004 SARS [Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome] outbreak. Late 2019 and early 2020 has seen a rapid spread of the novel Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) that caused COVID 19 pandemic. The US-FDA [Food and Drug Administration] has approved Hydroxychloroquine as potential treatments to COVID 19 [or SARS-CoV-2] coronavirus. However Hydroxychloroquine is linked to several side effects like retinal toxicity, neuromyotoxicity, ocular toxicity and retinopathy. Uncertainty in the mode of action, specificity and risks of Hydroxychloroquine against coronavirus makes it extremely unclear whether it is a viable medication for treatment or not. Nevertheless, the drug is gaining notability like never before in the existing state of affairs.

In this review, we discuss the current literature on the structural characteristics, pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics data, benefits and novel applications of Hydroxychloroquine, its immunomodulatory mechanism with respect to each application and the potential side effects associated with it. The present scenario compels critical care physicians and researchers worldwide to undertake several studies emphasising the role of Hydroxychloroquine as a potential drug.

Keywords: Antiinflammatory, Antimalarial, Chloroquine, Hydroxychloroquine, Quinine, Treatment.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Anique Ajmal,**

THQ Hospital, Sadiqabad, Rahim Yar Khan.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Anique Ajmal et al, *A Review On Efficacy And Safety Of Hydroxychloroquine Against Viral* , Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(09).

INTRODUCTION:

Quinine was universally the first antimalarial drug that proved to be effective against malaria and other inflammatory diseases in 1894 as reported by Payne in his studies. It is a well-established fact that around the year 1630 the value of cinchona bark was well known in Peru and was used to cure malaria. Cinchona bark and its clinical significance started to be spread quickly all over Europe [1]. By 1669 the bark was described in early German pharmacopoeias and in 1677 it appeared even in the London pharmacopoeia. In 1738, the French explorer De la Condamine identified the tree from which the bark was taken and named it quinquina. Carl von Linne in his *Genera plantarum* of year 1742 classified it as a representative of a new genus and renamed it *Cinchona* [2]. The bark was used to extract the phytochemicals in 1820, and named by Pierre Joseph Pelletier and Joseph Caventou as Quinine that replaced the bark as the standard treatment for malaria [3]. Quinine remained the forerunner of malaria treatment until the 1920s, when more effective synthetic anti-malarial like Chloroquine came to use in the 1940's [4]. With resistance developed against Chloroquine in some parts of the world, a new derivative Hydroxychloroquine was introduced in 1955 and differs from Chloroquine only by a hydroxyl group, decreasing its toxicity while conserving its efficacy.

Hydroxychloroquine is a well-established antimalarial approved in 1950's. Sold under the brand name Plaquenil, it is used as a treatment to wide spectrum of diseases. Chloroquine and Hydroxychloroquine are the two important antimalarial derivatives of Quinine. These have been used since the 1950s for the treatment of various inflammatory, rheumatic diseases like Lupus erythematosus, infections with intracellular microorganisms and several other dermatologic diseases [5]. They are used as primary treatments in viral infections lacking drugs [6]. These antimalarial agents Chloroquine and Hydroxychloroquine lead to improvement of clinical and laboratory parameters, but their slow onset of action distinguishes them from glucocorticoids and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory agents (NSAID) [7].

Hydroxychloroquine possess an immunomodulatory mechanism of action to target the diseases. It has an established efficacy against Systemic Lupus Erythematosus, Rheumatoid Arthritis, Palindromic rheumatism, Eosinophilic fasciitis, Dermatomyositis, Sjögren's syndrome, Porphyria cutanea tarda, Polymorphous light eruption, Granuloma annular, Lichen planus, Lupus panniculitis and Discoid lupus [8]. It is reported that patients with quiescent lupus erythematosus taking Hydroxychloroquine are less

likely to have clinical manifestations if they are maintained on the same drug [9]. Hydroxychloroquine is also recommended to pregnant women with Lupus erythematosus as it does not possess fetal toxicity [10].

There are many proposed mechanisms of action of Hydroxychloroquine such as increase in PH of the cellular components, interference with DNA stabilization and cell signaling, activation of immune cells and inhibition of proteases. However, the specific mechanism in individual disease is not very clear. Uncertainty in the mode of action, specificity and risks of Hydroxychloroquine questions its viability as a potential treatment. In this review we discuss the structural characteristics of Hydroxychloroquine and its novel applications.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

We conducted a literature search using four databases (PubMed, Embase, Web of Science, and Clinicaltrials.gov). Our search strategy included MeSH terms and key words for hydroxychloroquine including trade names and generic names from date of inception to January 2020. A total of 587 articles were screened, and after excluding review articles, duplicates, and non-relevant articles, we included seven articles reporting clinical use of hydroxychloroquine use in general clinical practice

Review:

Stereochemistry of hydroxychloroquine:

Hydroxychloroquine is an important chiral drug with symbolic optical activity. The pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics properties of the molecule are stereo-selective. Animal studies and other In-vitro studies indicate that the several metabolic pathways could express stereo-selectivity of Hydroxychloroquine [12]. Hydroxychloroquine is a racemic mixture consisting of an R and S enantiomer [13]. The enantiomers of hydroxychloroquine have very long terminal phase half-lives [14]. A sequential achiral—chiral high-performance liquid chromatographic system has been developed for the determination of the enantiomers of hydroxychloroquine, (+)-HCQ and (-)-HCQ [15]. (R)- (-)-hydroxychloroquine (the stereo-chemical 'rectus' configuration of hydroxychloroquine) is present at higher concentrations in the blood than (S)- (+)-hydroxychloroquine (the stereo-chemical 'sinister' configuration of hydroxychloroquine), suggesting the existence of stereo-selective processes in the deposition and metabolism of this drug [16]. (S)- (+)-HCQ enantiomer undergoes more rapid elimination compared to the (R)- (-)-HCQ, probably due to more rapid hepatic metabolism and excretion

[17]. The efficacy and safety of the drug enantiomers might also differ and needs to be studied further [18].

Mechanism of action:

Hydroxychloroquine can be summarized to have an immunomodulatory effect on the host cell. The major proposed mechanism of the molecule on the immune system involves its intervention in lysosomal acidification [19], chemotaxis and phagocytosis. It increases pH within intracellular vacuoles and alter processes such as protein degradation by enzymes like acidic hydrolases in the lysosome. It inhibits proteolysis in immune cells by targeting metalloproteinases [20, 21]. This in turn influences the assembly of macromolecules in endosomes and posttranslational modification of proteins within Golgi apparatus. Hydroxychloroquine reduces the production of interleukins and other cytokines [22]. It behaves as a potent antagonist to prostaglandins and inhibits key enzymes like phospholipase A2 [23]. It hinders UV light absorption and there by blocks subcutaneous reactions [24]. It interferes in the calcium mediated cell signaling pathways involved in the inhibition of T- cell and B- cell receptors [25]. Hydroxychloroquine is attributed to interfere with the 'antigen processing' in macrophages and other antigen presenting cells. Acidic cytoplasmic compartments are usually required for the antigenic protein to be digested and for the peptides to assemble with the α and β chains of MHC class II proteins. Hydroxychloroquine increases the acidity of lysosomes and diminishes the formation of peptide-MHC protein complexes required to stimulate CD4+ T cells. This results in down-regulation of the immune response against auto-antigenic peptides [7].

Hydroxychloroquine has also a strong binding to melanin. This reflects the ocular toxicity and dermatological properties Hydroxychloroquine. The occurrence of any ocular adverse reactions can however be minimized by paying close attention to the dose (based on a body weight) with regular retinal examination [26].

Hydroxychloroquine as an antimalarial agent:

Malaria is one of the most wide spread parasitic disease in the world with about 3 million deaths being attributed to this disease [27]. The causative agent for malaria is a unicellular eukaryote called Plasmodium. There are four species of plasmodium that cause malaria namely *P. falciparum*, *P. malaria*, *P. ovale* and *P. vivax*. Of the four species of Plasmodium, malaria caused by *P. vivax* is far more threatening [28]. Chloroquine that is chemically 4-aminoquinoline compound had been used for the prophylaxis and

treatment of malaria against Quinine resistant forms of plasmodium until 1960 [29]. With the onset of resistant plasmodium strains to Chloroquine, its N-ethyl substituted analogue Hydroxychloroquine was used as treatment to malaria since then. Hydroxychloroquine is preferred over Chloroquine when high doses are required because of low Ocular toxicity of Hydroxychloroquine over Chloroquine [30]. Hydroxychloroquine is known to actively attack the heme-polymerization process to disrupt the life cycle of the parasite. It is also viewed to passively interfere with the parasite's hemoglobin digestive pathway [31]. This mechanism however is similar to the antimalarial activity of Chloroquine.

Hydroxychloroquine as an antiviral agent:

Antimalarial such as Chloroquine and Hydroxychloroquine have long since been adopted to treat viral diseases. Studies have proved its efficacy on viruses like HIV, Influenza, SARS-CoV and members of Orthomyxoviridae. Chloroquine and hydroxychloroquine also are a valuable option to be tested in low-cost antiretroviral combinations, but correct dosages should be used, considering regularly monitoring to prevent retinopathy.

The antiviral effects of Hydroxychloroquine are attributed to the reduction in interleukins and inhibition of glycosylation of viral particles by specific interactions with glycosyltransferases [45]. Studies have proved that Hydroxychloroquine inhibits replication of the SARS coronavirus1 and Orthomyxoviridae [46]. Hydroxychloroquine has recently been shown to inhibit Quinone reductase which is involved in sialic acid biosynthesis [47]. This effect explains the effects of hydroxychloroquine on HIV and SARS coronavirus as sialic acid is an integral part of HIV glycoproteins and SARS coronavirus receptor. It also explains the in-vitro effects of Hydroxychloroquine on Orthomyxoviruses which use sialic acid moieties as receptors [48].

The broad-spectrum antiviral effects of Hydroxychloroquine deserve particular attention especially at a time like now in which the world is threatened by the possibility of a new Corona virus pandemic, and the availability of effective drugs would be fundamental during evaluation of an effective vaccine.

Other effects of hydroxychloroquine:

1. Antithrombotic effect:

Hydroxychloroquine exhibits antithrombotic effect by inhibition of platelet aggregation and adhesion, increasing endothelium dependent vasodilation and

artery elasticity, reducing vascular stiffness and vascular resistance [49].

2. Anti-neoplastic effect:

Clinical studies on cancer patients reveal with chronic lymphatic leukemia that Hydroxychloroquine induces apoptosis of malignant B-cells, by activating caspase-3 and modifying Bcl-2/bax ratio [50, 51]. An In-vitro study using biodegradable nanoparticle drug delivery system revealed that Hydroxychloroquine has a strong apoptotic effect on B-lymphocytes [52]. Hydroxychloroquine has demonstrated In-vitro anti-proliferative effect on breast cancer cell and mouse colon cancer cell lines [8].

3. Dermatologic effect:

Hydroxychloroquine blocks UV light absorption by skin. This is viewed to inhibit subcutaneous light sensitive reactions or polymorphic light eruptions and reduce skin symptoms like rash [24].

Pharmacokinetic data of hydroxychloroquine:

Hydroxychloroquine is almost completely and rapidly absorbed after oral administration. It has a 45% protein binding capacity that is metabolized in liver and excreted biliary [$<10\%$] and largely through kidneys [$>25\%$]. It has a bioavailability [Tmax] of 2 to 4.5 hours and a half-life of 32-50 days.

Hydroxychloroquine is metabolized in the liver into three active metabolites: desethylchloroquine, desethylhydroxychloroquine, and bisdesethylhydroxychloroquine [53].

CONCLUSION:

Hydroxychloroquine and other antimalarial drugs since the first use nearly a century ago, have exhibited protracted effects on diseases in nearly all major branches of medicine including immunology, oncology, hematology, dermatology, cardiology, and infectious diseases. This drug hydroxychloroquine works partially by inactivating the body's immune response like inflammation, edema, pain, fever and disrupts critical cell processes. Recent Clinical study reports from China and France have associated Chloroquine, Hydroxychloroquine in combination with antiviral drug like azithromycin to reduction in fever, decrease in lung lesions, delayed disease progression and reduction in the viral load in patients with COVID-19. The exact mechanism however, by which this drug works to resolve malaria and other diseases is largely unknown. *In-Vitro* studies have shown that hydroxychloroquine inhibits SARS-CoV-2 transmission through alkalisation of the intracellular phagolysosome, which prevents virion

fusion and un-coating and therefore curbs the viral spread.

Though hydroxychloroquine is effective, it is associated with the potential of causing numerous side effects, like headache, loss of appetite, nausea, vomiting, skin rash and in severe cases vision loss due to retinal toxicity. Chloroquine that is a close analogue to hydroxychloroquine is however considered less safe but equally effective.

One significant benefit with using these drugs is that they have been on the market and used for a sufficiently long time. Hence a reasonable amount of information regarding contraindications, allergic responses, side effects, and efficacy is available that can kept in mind before using it to treat new diseases like COVID-19. Since they have been around for so long, generic versions are available, which may prove to be cost-effective for use in coronavirus treatment worldwide.

FUTURE PROSPECTIVES:

Hydroxychloroquine and Chloroquine are well established effective and relatively safe drugs used to treat wide range of disorders from malaria to autoimmunity. There is a greater requirement to gather more information on their mode of action of these drugs with respect to all the mentioned disorders. This can further be used to develop formulations and combinations with enhanced therapeutic activity.

REFERENCES:

- Petri, M. (1996). Hydroxychloroquine [HCQ] use in the Baltimore Lupus Cohort: effects on lipids, glucose and thrombosis. *Lupus*, 5(1_suppl), 16-22
- Hofheinz, W., & Merkli, B. (1984). Quinine and quinine analogues. In *Antimalarial Drug II* (pp. 61-81). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Rosenthal, P. J. (Ed.). (2001). *Antimalarial chemotherapy: mechanisms of action, resistance, and new directions in drug discovery*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- Gustafsson, L. L., Beermann, B., & Abdi, Y. A. (1987). *Handbook of drugs for tropical parasitic infections*. Taylor and Francis Ltd
- Yam, J. C. S., & Kwok, A. K. H. (2006). Ocular toxicity of Hydroxychloroquine [HCQ]. *Hong Kong Medical Journal*, 12(4), 294.
- Colson, P., Rolain, J. M., Lagier, J. C., Brouqui, P., & Raoult, D. (2020). Chloroquine and hydroxychloroquine as available weapons to fight COVID-19. *Int J Antimicrob Agents*, 105932(10.1016).
- Fox, R. I. (1993, October). Mechanism of action of Hydroxychloroquine [HCQ] as an

- antirheumatic drug. In *Seminars in arthritis and rheumatism* (Vol. 23, No. 2, pp. 82-91). WB Saunders.
8. Ben-Zvi, I., Kivity, S., Langevitz, P., & Shoenfeld, Y. (2012). Hydroxychloroquine [HCQ]: from malaria to autoimmunity. *Clinical reviews in allergy & immunology*, 42(2), 145-153.
 9. Canadian Hydroxychloroquine [HCQ] Study Group*. (1991). A randomized study of the effect of withdrawing Hydroxychloroquine [HCQ] sulfate in systemic lupus erythematosus. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 324(3), 150-154.
 10. Clowse, M. E., Magder, L., Witter, F., & Petri, M. (2006). Hydroxychloroquine [HCQ] in lupus pregnancy. *Arthritis & Rheumatism: Official Journal of the American College of Rheumatology*, 54(11), 3640-3647.
 11. National Center for Biotechnology Information. PubChem Database. Hydroxychloroquine, [Compound-ID] CID = 3652, [https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Hydroxychloroquine]
 12. Cardoso, C. D., & Bonato, P. S. (2009). Enantioselective metabolism of hydroxychloroquine employing rats and mice hepatic microsomes. *Brazilian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 45(4), 658-667.
 13. Furst, D. E. (1996). Pharmacokinetics of hydroxychloroquine and chloroquine during treatment of rheumatic diseases. *Lupus*, 5(1_suppl), 11-15.
 14. Midha, K. K., Hubbard, J. W., Rawson, M. J., McKay, G., & Schwede, R. (1996). The roles of stereochemistry and partial areas in a parallel design study to assess the bioequivalence of two formulations of hydroxychloroquine: a drug with a very long half life. *European journal of pharmaceutical sciences*, 4(5), 283-292.
 15. Iredale, J., & Wainer, I. W. (1992). Determination of hydroxychloroquine and its major metabolites in plasma using sequential achiral—chiral high-performance liquid chromatography. *Journal of Chromatography B: Biomedical Sciences and Applications*, 573(2), 253-258.
 16. Rainsford, K. D., Parke, A. L., Clifford-Rashotte, M., & Kean, W. F. (2015). Therapy and pharmacological properties of hydroxychloroquine and chloroquine in treatment of systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis and related diseases. *Inflammopharmacology*, 23(5), 231-269.
 17. Ducharme, J., Fieger, H., Ducharme, M. P., Khalil, S. K., & Wainer, I. W. (1995). Enantioselective disposition of hydroxychloroquine after a single oral dose of the racemate to healthy subjects [see comments]. *British journal of clinical pharmacology*, 40(2), 127-133.
 18. Schrezenmeier, E., & Dörner, T. (2020). Mechanisms of action of hydroxychloroquine and chloroquine: implications for rheumatology. *Nature Reviews Rheumatology*, 1-12.
 19. Ohkuma, S., & Poole, B. (1978). Fluorescence probe measurement of the intralysosomal pH in living cells and the perturbation of pH by various agents. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 75(7), 3327-3331.
 20. Ziegler, H. K., & Unanue, E. R. (1982). Decrease in macrophage antigen catabolism caused by ammonia and chloroquine is associated with inhibition of antigen presentation to T cells. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 79(1), 175-178.
 21. Lesiak, A., Narbutt, J., Sysa-Jedrzejowska, A., Lukamowicz, J., McCauliffe, D. P., & Wóźniacka, A. (2010). Effect of chloroquine phosphate treatment on serum MMP-9 and TIMP-1 levels in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *Lupus*, 19(6), 683-688.
 22. Sperber, K., Quraishi, H. U. M. A., Kalb, T. H., Panja, A. S. I. T., Stecher, V., & Mayer, L. (1993). Selective regulation of cytokine secretion by hydroxychloroquine: inhibition of interleukin 1 alpha (IL-1-alpha) and IL-6 in human monocytes and T cells. *The Journal of Rheumatology*, 20(5), 803-808.
 23. Löffler, B. M., Bohn, E., Hesse, B., & Kunze, H. (1985). Effects of antimalarial drugs on phospholipase A and lysophospholipase activities in plasma membrane, mitochondrial, microsomal and cytosolic subcellular fractions of rat liver. *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Lipids and Lipid Metabolism*, 835(3), 448-455.
 24. Lester, R. S., Burnham, T. K., Fine, G., & Murray, K. (1967). Immunologic concepts of light reactions in lupus erythematosus and polymorphous light eruptions: I. The mechanism of action of hydroxychloroquine. *Archives of dermatology*, 96(1), 1-10.
 25. Goldman, F. D., Gilman, A. L., Hollenback, C., Kato, R. M., Premack, B. A., & Rawlings, D. J. (2000). Hydroxychloroquine inhibits calcium signals in T cells: a new mechanism to explain its immunomodulatory properties. *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology*, 95(11), 3460-3466.
 26. Rainsford, K. D., Parke, A. L., Clifford-Rashotte, M., & Kean, W. F. (2015). Therapy and pharmacological properties of

- hydroxychloroquine and chloroquine in treatment of systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis and related diseases. *Inflammopharmacology*, 23(5), 231-269.
27. Sachs, J., & Malaney, P. (2002). The economic and social burden of malaria. *Nature*, 415(6872), 680-685.
28. Galinski, M. R., & Barnwell, J. W. (1996). *Plasmodium vivax*: Merozoites, invasion of reticulocytes and considerations for malaria vaccine development. *Parasitology today*, 12(1), 20-29.
29. Terkuile, F., White, N. J., Holloway, P., Pasvol, G., & Krishna, S. (1993). *Plasmodium falciparum*: in vitro studies of the pharmacodynamic properties of drugs used for the treatment of severe malaria. *Experimental parasitology*, 76(1), 85-95.
30. Easterbrook, M. (1999). Detection and prevention of maculopathy associated with antimalarial agents. *International ophthalmology clinics*, 39(2), 49-57.
31. Slater, A. F. G., & Cerami, A. (1992). Inhibition by chloroquine of a novel haem polymerase enzyme activity in malaria trophozoites. *Nature*, 355(6356), 167-169.
32. Rainsford, K. D., Parke, A. L., Clifford-Rashotte, M., & Kean, W. F. (2015). Therapy and pharmacological properties of hydroxychloroquine and chloroquine in treatment of systemic lupus erythematosus, rheumatoid arthritis and related diseases. *Inflammopharmacology*, 23(5), 231-269.
33. James, J. A., Kim-Howard, X. R., Bruner, B. F., Jonsson, M. K., McClain, M. T., Arbuckle, M. R., ... & Harley, J. B. (2007). Hydroxychloroquine sulfate treatment is associated with later onset of systemic lupus erythematosus. *Lupus*, 16(6), 401-409.
34. Willis, R., Seif, A. M., McGwin Jr, G., Martinez-Martinez, L. A., Gonzalez, E. B., Dang, N., ... & Alarcón, G. S. (2012). Effect of hydroxychloroquine treatment on pro-inflammatory cytokines and disease activity in SLE patients: data from LUMINA (LXXV), a multiethnic US cohort. *Lupus*, 21(8), 830-835.
35. Weber, S. M., & Levitz, S. M. (2000). Chloroquine interferes with lipopolysaccharide-induced TNF- α gene expression by a nonlysosomal mechanism. *The Journal of Immunology*, 165(3), 1534-1540.
36. Wozniacka, A., Lesiak, A., Narbutt, J., McCauliffe, D. P., & Sysa-Jedrzejowska, A. (2006). Chloroquine treatment influences proinflammatory cytokine levels in systemic lupus erythematosus patients. *Lupus*, 15(5), 268-275.
37. López, P., Gómez, J., Mozo, L., Gutiérrez, C., & Suárez, A. (2006). Cytokine polymorphisms influence treatment outcomes in SLE patients treated with antimalarial drugs. *Arthritis research & therapy*, 8(2), R42.
38. Kawasaki, T., & Kawai, T. (2014). Toll-like receptor signaling pathways. *Frontiers in immunology*, 5, 461.
39. Means, T. K., Latz, E., Hayashi, F., Murali, M. R., Golenbock, D. T., & Luster, A. D. (2005). Human lupus autoantibody-DNA complexes activate DCs through cooperation of CD32 and TLR9. *The Journal of clinical investigation*, 115(2), 407-417.
40. Lafyatis, R., York, M., & Marshak-Rothstein, A. (2006). Antimalarial agents: Closing the gate on toll-like receptors?. *Arthritis & Rheumatism: Official Journal of the American College of Rheumatology*, 54(10), 3068-3070.
41. Wallace, D. J. (1994). The effect of hydroxychloroquine therapy on serum levels of immunoregulatory molecules in patients with systemic lupus erythematosus. *J Rheumatol*, 21, 375-376.
42. Fox, R. I., & Kang, H. I. (1993). Mechanism of action of antimalarial drugs: inhibition of antigen processing and presentation. *Lupus*, 2(1_suppl), 9-12.
43. Yin, H., Wu, H., Chen, Y., Zhang, J., Zheng, M., Chen, G., ... & Lu, Q. (2018). The therapeutic and pathogenic role of autophagy in autoimmune diseases. *Frontiers in immunology*, 9, 1512.
44. Kimmelman, A. C. (2011). The dynamic nature of autophagy in cancer. *Genes & development*, 25(19), 1999-2010.
45. Savarino, A., Lucia, M. B., Rastrelli, E., Rutella, S., Golotta, C., Morra, E., ... & Cauda, R. (2004). Anti-HIV effects of chloroquine: inhibition of viral particle glycosylation and synergism with protease inhibitors. *JAIDS Journal of Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndromes*, 35(3), 223-232.
46. Miller, D. K., & Lenard, J. (1981). Antihistaminics, local anesthetics, and other amines as antiviral agents. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 78(6), 3605-3609.
47. Kwiek, J. J., Haystead, T. A., & Rudolph, J. (2004). Kinetic mechanism of quinone oxidoreductase 2 and its inhibition by the antimalarial quinolines. *Biochemistry*, 43(15), 4538-4547.
48. Olofsson, S., Kumlin, U., Dimock, K., & Arnberg, N. (2005). Avian influenza and sialic acid receptors: more than meets the eye?. *The Lancet infectious diseases*, 5(3), 184-188.

49. Tang, C., Godfrey, T., Stawell, R., & Nikpour, M. (2012). Hydroxychloroquine in lupus: emerging evidence supporting multiple beneficial effects. *Internal medicine journal*, 42(9), 968-978.
50. Lagneaux, L., Delforge, A., Carlier, S., Massy, M., Bernier, M., & Bron, D. (2001). Early induction of apoptosis in B-chronic lymphocytic leukaemia cells by hydroxychloroquine: activation of caspase-3 and no protection by survival factors. *British journal of haematology*, 112(2), 344-352.
51. Lagneaux, L., Delforge, A., Dejeneffe, M., Massy, M., Bernier, M., & Bron, D. (2002). Hydroxychloroquine-induced apoptosis of chronic lymphocytic leukemia involves activation of caspase-3 and modulation of Bcl-2/bax/ratio. *Leukemia & lymphoma*, 43(5), 1087-1095.
52. Mansilla, E., Marin, G. H., Nunez, L., Drago, H., Sturla, F., Mertz, C., ... & Raimondi, C. (2010). The lysosomotropic agent, hydroxychloroquine, delivered in a biodegradable nanoparticle system, overcomes drug resistance of B-chronic lymphocytic leukemia cells in vitro. *Cancer Biotherapy and Radiopharmaceuticals*, 25(1), 97-103.
53. McChesney, E. W., Conway, W. D., Banks, W. F., Rogers, J. E., Shekosky, J. M., Grace, A. J., ... & Sullivan, D. J. (1966). Studies of the metabolism of some compounds of the 4-amino-7-chloroquinoline series. *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, 151(3), 482-493.